

WORKING TOGETHER TO BUILD BRIDGES

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1. ABSTRACT

Backed by the UK Department of Transport within the "LINK" scheme, a programme was completed to assemble mechanical performance data necessary for the use of advanced composite materials in Civil Engineering. A full size beam structure, the largest composite structure of its kind, was subjected to nine months of natural weathering under load and its performance continuously monitored. Results show that composite structures can be designed accurately and the environmentally resistant properties of composites offer real advantages in service life and reduced maintenance. A 120m footbridge over the River Tay was built to demonstrate the potential of this remarkable system.

Keywords: Vetrotex; Roving; UNIFILO; Advanced Composites; Pultrusion; Civil Engineering; Bridges; Environmental Resistance.

2. INTRODUCTION

Growth in both passenger and freight transport and increasing average weight of containers is applying greater pressure on transport networks. Scope is foreseen for developing construction systems and materials to minimise lifetime costs, perhaps over decades. If maintenance can be reduced, time delays will be reduced, as the proportion of the transport network out of service is minimised. One approach towards this goal has been identified by the UK Department of Transport as "Novel Designs of Structures, to carry heavier loads within constrained dimensions" (1). Materials of construction with improved corrosion resistance, caused mainly by chlorides (road salt) and weathering, will greatly contribute to reduced maintenance.

It is recognised that pultrusion offers a process for manufacturing composites with high, predictable and consistent performance, and that the full potential for pultruded structures has not been realised due to the difficulties of bonding straight profiles to form useful 3-dimensional structures without sacrificing these properties. Furthermore, the excellent corrosion and weathering resistance of composites would make such materials an attractive proposition for low maintenance highway structures.

This problem began to be tackled by Maunsell Structural Plastics about ten years ago when they recognised the possibilities of composites (2). The result is the unique and patented "Advanced Composites Construction System", or ACCS (See Note 1). Using this modular construction system, with Maunsell's own "Limit State Design" technique for composites (3), it is possible to design and build truly structural, mainly 2-dimensional civil engineering structures quickly and efficiently to within 5-10% of experimental test values (4).

3. SYSTEM COMPONENTS

The basis of the ACCS system is a pultruded plank, 600mm wide by 80mm deep, in a hollow section containing six vertical supporting walls between the two faces. The plank edges feature a keyway slot with moulded-in undercuts; the section thickness is 3.5mm. The planks are assembled together using special connecting pieces having "dogbone" ridges along their length corresponding to the plank slots. The connecting profiles are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Components of the ACCS System

Assembly may be performed under factory conditions, or, with suitable precautions on-site. This is important where large structures are concerned and where factory assembly, or transportation, is not possible.

4. COMPONENT MANUFACTURE

The pultruded sections are manufactured to a rigorous, Maunsell specification, using polyester resin reinforced with alternate layers of glass rovings and continuous strand mat. A surface tissue incorporated in the exposed face provides a resin-rich surface having good weathering performance.

The rovings employed are R099 P122 direct rovings from Vetrotex, used in conjunction with UNIFILO U501 continuous strand mat, specially developed for pultrusion. For the plank, 800 ends of roving are used with 22 rolls of UNIFILO mat of various widths at 450g/m²; the glass content achieved is between 60 and 65% by weight. The reinforcement is impregnated within a chamber fed with resin under pressure, immediately prior to the die proper: The resin used may be pigmented and filled as required. The "LINK" programme resin was a special Class 1 fire retardant resin (B.S. 476; Part 7). Cure takes place within the die at about 140-160 deg.C. in only 2-4 minutes, depending on section thickness. On leaving the die, the solid profile is

gripped by pullers which pull the materials through the production line. (Figure 2.). Component properties are assessed by a full programme of type approval and batch testing, combined with lot traceability within a quality framework. The longest continuous pultruded section made so far is 18 metres, although there is no reason why this should not be increased to any desired length, subject to available space and transport limitations. Sub-assembly and bonding may be carried out in the factory to take advantage of controlled conditions and the benefits of less on-site working.

Figure 2. The Pultrusion Process

The geometric and some important Material Properties of the ACCS components are given in Table 1.

5. THE "LINK" PROGRAMME

5.1 Background: The considerable potential for advanced composites in construction has already been referred to. Areas of major interest in highway structures are: footbridges, sign gantries and lightly trafficked bridges. Advances in analysis, design and production technology are expected to make composites competitive with aluminium, steel and concrete, and offer significant advantages in weight, as well as in initial and life maintenance costs (5). Examples are already appearing on our roads (Figure 3). For composites to gain acceptance in more demanding bonded 3-dimensional highway structures, further research into long term performance under severe environmental conditions was needed.

Maunsell SP therefore instigated a "LINK" programme, having this as its objective, to be undertaken by the following consortium of partners:-

GOVERNMENT DEPARTMENTS:	The Department of Transport The Science & Engineering Research Council
LEAD PARTNER:	Maunsell Structural Plastics
INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS:	University of Surrey (Academic Research) Vetrotex (Glass Reinforcements) DSM Resins (Pultrusion Resins) Ciba-Geigy (Adhesives) CU Bridges (Civil Engineers)

Table 1. PROPERTIES OF THE ACCS COMPONENTS

a) Geometric Properties

Component	Reference	Overall Dimensions (mm)	Typical Wall Thickness (mm)	Weight (Kg/m)
Plank	Ref P	600x80	3.5	11.0
3-Way Connector	Ref B	80x80	3.5	2.2
Groove Connector	Ref C	80x40	4.0	2.3
Toggle Connector	Ref T	-	-	0.5
Flat Trimmer	Ref F	80x10	4.0	0.9
Channel Connector	Ref U	80x88	3.5	1.8

b) Material Properties

Axial Modulus	20-25,000 MPa
Transverse Flexural Modulus	10-13,000 MPa
Surface Spread of Flame	Class 0-2 to B.S. 476; Pt 7
Thermal Resistance, U-value (Foam filled)	0.3-0.45 W/m ² K

The programme lasted for 18 months, being completed in February 1993, and examined environmental effects of moisture, temperature and solar radiation - sustained and cyclical - in addition to short term mechanical properties and, where practical, time dependent load effects such as creep and fatigue.

5.2 Work Programme: Tests were carried out on both full scale structures exposed to natural weathering, and to samples of panels and bonded joints subjected to accelerated ageing regimes.

a) Two full size box beams, as shown in Figure 4, were constructed and put on test under their full design load of 20 tonnes for nine months in the test rig shown in Figure 5. Each beam measured 2m wide by 700mm deep by 18m long and weighed 3 tonnes. Regular inspections were carried out and a NDT programme executed to determine their stiffness, natural frequency and creep deformation. Strain gauges monitored stresses at critical points and temperatures, both in and out of the shade were recorded. At the end of the tests, one of the beams was tested to destruction.

b) Test coupons were used to determine the short term behaviour, and the effect of accelerated ageing on this, of both panels and bonded joints. The tests included rigidity, tensile strength, impact strength and fatigue resistance. Ageing schedules included temperature and moisture cycles and UV radiation. Coefficients of thermal and moisture expansion were also determined.

5.3 Results: a) Weathering of the box beams under full design load (200kN), resulted in very little, less than 5%, reduction in beam stiffness; the slight variations actually recorded being possibly due to temperature differences at the time of loading and the different loading procedures used. The experimental deflections at the beam centre averaged 17.4mm. Dynamic testing to determine the natural frequency of vibration of the beams also showed little change during the test period, providing further evidence that no significant structural damage had been sustained.

One of the beams was subjected to a test to failure after the exposure programme. The laboratory rig used for this purpose was similar to that employed for the environmental test, with a central span of 3.00m. The beam failed at 625kN total load by shear failure associated with a crushing/buckling of the diaphragms at the support load line; a result which demonstrated the beam's ability to withstand the applied severe loading extremely well. It is worth noting that the ultimate load represented a factor of more than three times the maximum design load of the beam and demonstrated the full effectiveness of the bonded joints.

b) Results from the coupon sample tests now allow a full set of design data to be collated, enabling accurate in-service predictions to be made for future structures based on ACCS.

6. THE "LINKLEADER" PROJECT

6.1 Background: During the "LINK" programme, a request for assistance was received from the University of Dundee, who had been approached by the Aberfeldy Golf Club (Tayside) who needed a footbridge across the River Tay to connect their course with newly acquired land to extend their grounds. With restricted funds, the Club looked for help to reduce the building costs. This provided an excellent opportunity for demonstrating the ACCS system. With only minor changes another consortium was established to subsidise the bridge both in cost and practical assistance. This consortium was made up of the following:

PROJECT MANAGER & CHIEF DESIGNER: Maunsell Structural Plastics

RAW MATERIAL SUPPLIERS:	Vetrotex (UK)	- Glass Fibres
	Scott-Bader Co	- Resins
	Ciba-Geigy	- Adhesives
COMPONENT MANUFACTURERS:	GEC Reinforced Plastics	- Pultruder
	Linear Composites	- Fibre Cables

CONSTRUCTION & ENG SUPPORT: O'Rourke Civil Engineering
University of Dundee

6.2 Design: The bridge is a cable stayed design with a 63m main span, a width of 2.23m and overall length of approximately 120m. The ACCS deck is supported by 17.5m high ACCS towers through "Parafil" (aramid fibre) cable stays. Additional "Parafil" stressing was used to provide aerodynamic stability.

6.3 Manufacture & Assembly: After site excavation and foundation work had been completed, the support towers were delivered from GEC, assembled and raised into their vertical positions using temporary ropes attached to the deck support beams and cables. The main span deck section was assembled and bonded together on site, before being winched across the river over the cross beams. Once in position, the cable stays and deck could be firmly anchored and the finishing touches, such as handrails and approach ramps, added. The lightweight components enabled this major bridge to be constructed with no on-site craneage, and only a small labour force in just over eight weeks.

6.4 Case History Study: The Aberfeldy Bridge was opened on 3rd October 1992. Since then, it has been exposed to the most rigorous weather conditions expected in that location and has survived intact and without any structural damage whatsoever. These included:-

- weight loading imposed by 1m (3ft) depth of snow;
- rapid temperature change from -1 to +11 deg.C. within 24 hours;
- highest ever recorded rise in river level, 3m (10ft);
- over 160Km/hr wind speed, with gusts up to 240Km/hr.

Further monitoring of the structure by the University of Dundee over an extended period will be invaluable in assessing the long term behaviour of the bridge (Figure 6.).

7. CONCLUSIONS

The "LINK" programme has demonstrated that the Limit State Design technique developed by Maunsell Structural Plastics with the ACCS system enables a remarkable correlation between theory and practice to be achieved. Experience gained from environmental tests further increase confidence that advanced composite materials must now be regarded as fully proven, viable materials of construction for structural applications.

8. REFERENCES

1. "LINK Transport Infrastructure and Operations Programme", The Department of Transport & SERC, November 1989.
2. Head, P.R., "GRP Walkway Membranes for Bridge Access and Protection", British Plastics Federation RP Group Congress, 1982.
3. Head, P.R. & Templemen, R.B., "The Application of Limit State Design Principles to Fibre Reinforced Plastics", British Plastics Federation RP Group Congress, 1986.
4. "Building a Better Future with Composites", Reinforced Plastics, pp32-37, September 1992, Elsevier Science Publishers.
5. Designer Composites Technology, Product Data Sheet, "ACCS".

NOTE 1: All rights pertaining to the ACCS system have been assigned to Designer Composites Technology Ltd., Alton, Hants, UK.

Figure 3. A Motorway Sign Gantry in ACCS

Figure 4. A Prototype ACCS Beam Under Construction

Figure 5. ACCS Prototype Beams Under Test at the University of Surrey

Figure 6. The Completed Aberfeldy Footbridge

